

EARLY-STAGE FATIGUE DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT OF A NON-CRIMP 3D ORTHOGONAL WEAVE COMPOSITE LOADED IN THE WARP AND WEFT DIRECTIONS

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Abstract

A detailed microstructural study of early stage fatigue damage development in a 3D non-crimp orthogonal weave composite has been carried out. Specimens were tension-tension fatigue cycled in both the warp and weft directions at peak stresses corresponding to peak strains of about 0.4%. Damage for both directions included transverse matrix cracking in the off-axis tows and in the resin-rich regions between the off-axis tows. For specimens fatigued in the warp direction, damage also includes Z-binder debonds and micro-delaminations between surface weft tows and adjacent warp tows. For weft fatigue loaded specimens, unusual triangular-shaped damage regions, which appear in pairs in a plan view of the specimens, are the consequence of a complex combination of damage. This consists of interfacial fracture between the Z-binder and the surface weft tow, debonding of the Z-binder from the central weft tow, and interfacial fracture between the central weft tow and the adjacent resin pocket.

1. Introduction

Composites with through-thickness reinforcement are an area of increasing research interest as they have been shown to improve the delamination resistance by increasing the through-thickness strength [1]. The addition of through-thickness reinforcement is typically achieved by stitching [2], Z-pinning [3], or weaving 3D fabrics with dedicated through-thickness, reinforcing Z-binders (also called Z-tows) [4]. For 3D woven preforms much of the work in the literature has been focussed on behaviour under quasi-static loading conditions [5-17]. Combined, these works address the effect of weaving on the mechanical properties, damage development, the effect of binder paths, and failure modes. In comparison, work undertaken under fatigue loading conditions is relatively limited [e.g. 1, 18-22], especially with regards to a detailed damage development assessment. In the present study, early stage damage development for fatigue loading in both principal directions (warp and weft) is reported. The work is part of a larger study aimed at improving the cost-effectiveness, in relation to fatigue behaviour and other properties, of 3D woven composites.

2. Experimental Techniques

The 3D non-crimp orthogonal woven E-glass fabric composite used here was supplied by 3TEX and has been termed “3D-78” due to its areal density of 78oz/yd², or 2.64kg/m². Although taken from a different batch, this fabric is identical to the one used in previous studies [5], [6]. There are three weft

layers, two warp layers, and Z-yarns interlacing along the warp direction (Figure 1). The warp, weft, and Z-direction consists of fibre tows from the PPG Hybon 2022 series; each warp and weft layer uses 2275 tex and 1500 tex fibre rovings respectively, while the Z-yarns use 276 tex. Of the total fibre volume content, 47.6% of fibres lie along the warp direction, 47.8% lie along the weft direction, and the remaining 4.6% lie in the z-direction. More specific details relating to the fabric can be found in [5].

Figure 1: 3D schematic diagram of a unit cell in the 3D-78 preform [5]

Specimens were manufactured using a three part resin and a wet impregnation technique described in [23]. The resin system consists of Epoxide Resin 300, nadic methyl anhydride (MNA) curing agent, and the accelerator Ancamine K61B. The combination of this resin system with E-glass fibres allows for the production of transparent specimens as the refractive index of the fibres and resin match closely. The fibre volume fraction content was approximately 0.44. Specimens were typically 230 mm in length. GFRP composite end tabs of length 50 mm were bonded to the ends of each specimen, leading to an overall gauge length of 130 mm. Specimen widths for the results reported here were 12 mm. The specimen thickness was nominally 2.1 mm.

Quasi-static tensile and tension-tension fatigue tests were performed using an Instron 1341 servohydraulic fatigue machine. Strain was measured using the Instron 2620 602 extensometer which has a standard gauge length of 12.5 mm and total travel of ± 2.5 mm. Standard extensometer gauge lengths were used for all quasi-static tensile tests, while the extensometer gauge length was extended to 96 mm during tensile-tensile fatigue tests. The quasi-static tests were all performed in tension and loaded at a rate of 1 mm/min until failure occurred. The fatigue tests were conducted under constant amplitude tension-tension conditions with a stress ratio of 0.1 and a frequency of 5 Hz. Images were taken at regular intervals under load during each test using a high resolution camera and a backlight to monitor the damage developed during testing. Using these images, specimens were sectioned along regions of interest; optical microscopy allowed these regions to be understood in relation to the composite geometry.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Quasi-static testing

In order to determine the mechanical properties of the 3D woven composite, quasi-static tensile tests were conducted in both principal directions. Six tests were carried out along the warp direction and eight tests along the weft with the main properties summarised in Table 1.

When comparing the warp and weft directions, it can be seen that the properties in both directions are essentially the same, though the modulus in the weft direction is slightly lower than that measured for the warp direction. These results seem reasonable since the fibre volume content is very similar in both directions. Comparing these results with those in [5], it is found that the modulus and ultimate strengths reported here are higher by approximately 10% and 20% respectively. The ultimate strains on the other hand are very similar. The differences may be the result of the different resin matrix and manufacturing method (a vinyl ester resin matrix and VARTM were used in [5]).

Table 1: Mechanical properties recorded for each principal fabric direction

Loading Direction	Elastic Modulus, E (GPa)	Ultimate Strength, σ_{ult} (MPa)	Ultimate Strain, ϵ_{ult} (%)
Warp	26.1 ± 0.7	519 ± 33	2.8 ± 0.2
Weft	25.3 ± 0.7	517 ± 28	2.8 ± 0.3

3.2. Fatigue damage development

In order to investigate the morphology of the early stage fatigue damage in tension-tension fatigue loading, tests were carried out on specimens at a peak stress level (100 MPa) for which the fatigue lifetimes in both the warp and weft directions were in excess of 1 million cycles. Observations reported here focus on the early stage damage development, with the specimens cycled for less than 100,000 cycles.

3.2.1. Damage development when loading in the warp direction

Figure 2 shows the early stage damage development in a transparent specimen before loading and after 25, 2000, 4000, 16000, and 32000 cycles. In the initial image of the unloaded/untested specimen (Figure 2a), the locations of the Z-binders, warp, and weft tows are indicated; there are also lighter coloured, resin-rich regions, traversing the width of the specimen, which separate each weft tow. In addition, about 16 small voids, of various sizes, are evident.

Under fatigue loading an immediate darkening of the weft tows could be seen at an early stage. Figure 2b shows this darkening after 25 cycles which is probably due to partial debonding of the 90° fibres from the matrix, similar to that reported in early work on cross-ply laminates by Bailey and Parvizi [24].

Figure 2c shows that the first easily visible damage initiates from the edge of the specimen as weft tow transverse matrix cracks propagating across the width. The crack highlighted in Figure 2c has been labelled “A” and its progressive growth across the width is shown in Figures 2d-g. In Figure 2e, there are regions where multiple transverse matrix cracks appear to have formed close together within a single weft tow. An example of this type of cracking has been highlighted at “B”. As will be shown subsequently, this can be explained by considering the geometry of the 3D fabric. Since there are three separated weft tow layers through the thickness of this fabric, transverse matrix cracks can form in each weft tow without necessarily occurring in the same through-thickness plane.

As well as weft tow transverse matrix cracks, some transverse cracks can be seen to form at the boundaries of weft tows or in the resin region between the boundaries of weft tows. Most of these transverse cracks are through-thickness, except where they intersect the warp tows or a Z-binder. One such crack has been highlighted and enlarged in Figure 2f. Compared with the weft tow transverse cracks, the accumulation rate for the transverse cracks associated with the boundaries of weft tows is much more rapid. In the plan view of the specimen shown in Figure 2g, the location where the boundary transverse cracks intersect Z-binders appears as a darkened region. These darkened regions form regularly along the length of the specimen, as can be seen in Figure 2g. The darkened regions are the consequence of interfacial cracking at the Z-binder (i.e. these are Z-binder debonds).

Associated with the weft tow transverse matrix cracks, tow-level interfacial fractures (micro-delaminations) develop between the weft tows and the warp tows (Figure 2f). These micro-delaminations are curved in shape and extend across the width of a specimen, terminating at the resin rich region between the warp tows associated with the location of the Z-binders, as highlighted in Figure 2g. As will be seen later, these micro-delaminations are associated with transverse matrix cracks which are within the weft tows (not the transverse cracks in the matrix pockets at, or between, weft tow boundaries).

Plan view images at higher magnification, and images of polished cross-sections at appropriate locations, enable the morphology of the 3D damage to be understood. Figure 3 consists of two images taken from another specimen fatigue loaded along the warp direction for 100,000 cycles at a peak stress of 100 MPa. The lower image shows the plan view of a specimen at higher magnification and the upper image is a cross-section of the same specimen at the same magnification, taken through the plane of a Z-binder. The plane of the cross-section of the upper image is indicated in the lower image by the line A-A'.

Figure 2: Photographs of a specimen fatigue loaded along the warp direction with a peak stress of 100MPa for approximately 60,000 cycles. All images were taken under continued loaded conditions after a number of cycles, except “a)” which occurred before testing. a) 0 cycles - unloaded (before testing); b) 25 cycles; c) 2000 cycles; d) 4000 cycles; e) 8000 cycles; f) 16000 cycles; g) 32000 cycles

A number of observations can be made from Figure 3. First, transverse matrix cracks in the weft tows, which apparently formed close together when looking at the plan view images, can be seen to be at different locations through the thickness of the composite; such an example is seen at “C”. Second, it was mentioned above, and highlighted in Figure 2f and g, that there are some transverse cracks which form between weft tow boundaries and extend across the thickness of the specimen, except where they terminate at warp tows or at Z-binders; at these locations, the Z-binder debonds appear as a darkened region. In the plan view image of Figure 3, two of these darkened regions have been indicated, at “D” and “E”. It can be observed from the cross-section that the darkened regions correspond to interfacial fractures at the Z-binder/resin pocket interface or at the Z-binder/weft tow interface i.e. Z-binder debonding has occurred. The Z-binder debonding at “D” and “E” has fully developed, while there is the beginning of Z-binder debonding at two locations at “F”. It should be noted that in all four examples shown in Figure 3, the Z-binder debonding is associated with a matrix crack at a weft tow boundary or in the resin pocket between weft tow boundaries. The debonding of the Z-binders in these plan view images appears similar to the damage found in [6] for tensile loading, and in [18] for fatigue loading. Both papers [6, 18] imply that these debonds occur at the interface between the Z-binder crown and a surface weft tow, but that does not appear to be the case here (it should be noted that in [6] and [18] a thicker non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven fabric, with four weft and three warp layers, was tested). Finally, a void can be seen in Figure 3; perhaps surprisingly, the void does not appear to be associated with the fatigue damage.

The geometry of the micro-delaminations which form between the weft tows and the warp tows can be seen in Figure 4 which shows a surface view and a cross-section indicated by the line B-B'. The cross

sectional image was taken approximately midway across the width of a warp tow and consequently, the Z-binder cannot be seen. The matrix cracks which appear sharply in the lower image, at “G” and “H”, can be seen to be in the upper surface weft tows (i.e. those nearer the camera) at G’ and H’. These weft tow matrix cracks are also associated with interfacial fractures between the surface weft tows and the adjacent warp tow; since these fractures lie in the plane of the interface between the weft and warp tows, it seems reasonable to refer to them as micro-delaminations. The weft tow matrix cracks at “J” and “K” are also associated with micro-delaminations at the weft tow/warp tow interface. Figure 4 also shows examples at “L” and “M” of transverse cracks between weft tow boundaries which extend across the thickness of the specimen, except where they meet the warp tows. There are no delaminations at the matrix/warp tow interface associated with these cracks, which suggests that the mismatch in Poisson’s ratio between the warp and weft tows leads to the micro-delaminations.

Figure 3: Cross-section and plan view photograph of a specimen fatigue loaded along the warp direction with a peak stress of 100 MPa for approximately 100,000 cycles. Both images have the same scale and show damage mechanisms such as Z-binder micro-debonds, transverse cracks between weft tow boundaries, and weft tow transverse matrix cracks

Figure 4: Cross-section and plan view photograph of a specimen fatigue loaded along the warp direction with a peak stress of 100 MPa for approximately 100,000 cycles. Both images have the same scale and show damage mechanisms including micro-delaminations, transverse cracks between weft tow boundaries, and weft tow transverse matrix cracks.

3.2.2. Damage development when loading in the weft direction

Figure 5 shows images of the early stage damage development of a specimen subjected to fatigue loading in the weft direction, at the same number of cycles as for Figures 1. Figure 5a shows an unloaded/untested specimen and the locations of the Z-binders, warp, and weft tows are indicated. Additionally, there are a small number of voids in the specimen. After 25 fatigue cycles (Figure 5b), a darkening of the warp tows can be seen which is again probably due to partial debonding of the 90° fibres from the surrounding matrix.

In a similar way to the specimens fatigued in the warp-direction described above, visible damage initiates as matrix cracks along both edges of the specimen, though this time growing in the warp tows (Figure 5c). A number of cracks initiate within each warp tow and slowly grow across the width of the specimen; examples have been highlighted at “N” in Figures 5c-g. After 32000 cycles, very few of these warp tow matrix cracks had extended completely across the specimen width. In Figure 5f and g, other cracks can be seen to have formed towards the centre of the specimen. Like the warp-direction loaded specimens, matrix cracks for weft-direction loading can form in different planes (there are two warp tow layers through the thickness).

In addition to transverse cracks forming in the warp tows, some transverse cracks can be seen to have formed through the Z-binder (Figure 5e). These cracks form anywhere across the width of the Z-binder, although many form toward its centre. Many of these cracks extend across the specimen width and through the thickness of the specimen as a single extended crack, as shown by the crack labelled “P” in

Figure 5e. Often, multiple cracks form along the length of the Z-binder, growing until they meet (presumably because stress-shielding then inhibits crack growth); an example is shown at “Q” in Figure 5f. Due to the geometry of a Z-binder, these cracks also create a fracture through the resin pockets. Compared with warp tow matrix cracks, cracks in this region propagate rapidly.

Figure 5: Photographs of a specimen fatigue loaded along the weft direction with a peak stress of 100MPa for approximately 60,000 cycles. All images were taken under continued loaded conditions after a number of cycles, except “a” which occurred before testing. a) 0 cycles - unloaded (before testing); b) 25 cycles; c) 2000 cycles; d) 4000 cycles; e) 8000 cycles; f) 16000 cycles; g) 32000 cycles

The most striking damage which develops when fatigue loading in the weft direction is the formation of unusual triangular-shaped damage; in Figures 5e-g, regions typical of this phenomenon are highlighted. These regions are associated with the transverse Z-binder cracks. In the plan view images of Figures 5f and g, the triangular-shaped damage occurs regularly with a noticeable, repeating pattern. From this pattern it can be noted that the triangular-shaped damage appears in pairs, with each pair facing in opposite directions. An example of one of the pairs is highlighted in Figures 5f and g with the label “R”. Measurements from micrographs have shown that each pair extends across half the width of a weft tow as well as the width of a Z-binder. As the micrographs described below will show, the triangular-shaped damage pairs are the result of interfacial debonding between the Z-binders and adjacent weft tows.

Before considering the triangular-shaped damage, the other types of damage will be discussed. Figure 6 shows a cross-section taken in the plane of a weft tow. Transverse warp tow matrix cracks at “S” can be seen, both in different tows and in different locations through the thickness. In addition to these cracks, through-thickness transverse cracks in the Z-binder and associated resin-rich pockets can be seen at “T”, “U”, and “V”. Some of these cracks (e.g. “U”) form in the middle of the Z-binder and extend through the middle of the resin pocket between warp tow boundaries. Others (e.g. at “T” and “V”), form near the edges of the Z-binder and extend along the edges of the warp tow boundaries. No micro-delaminations of the type found in the warp-direction specimens were observed in this weft specimen.

Figure 6: Specimen fatigued with a peak stress of 100MPa for approximately 60,000 cycles along the weft direction and sectioned along the weft plane (loading direction). The image displays various damage mechanisms including warp tow matrix cracks and Z-binder transverse cracks

The morphology of the triangular-shaped damage pairs can be understood with reference to Figure 7 where multiple cross-sections are shown across the width of a Z-binder. The six pairs of images in Figure 7 shows a plan view image (below) and a cross-section (above). In each plan view image, the red line shows the location of the complementary cross-section shown above; in moving from images 7(a) to 7(f), the red line sweeps from the bottom of the lower image to the top, showing the location of the polished cross-section. The morphology of the damage is complex: fundamentally it consists of (i) interfacial fracture between the Z-binder and the surface weft tow, (ii) debonding of the Z-binder from the central weft tow, and (iii) interfacial fracture between the central weft tow and the adjacent resin pocket. Although the Z-binder traverses asymmetrically from one surface of the composite to the opposite surface at this location, the apparent symmetry of the paired nature of the damage results from viewing the damage in the plan view.

Figure 7: Specimen fatigue loaded along the weft direction at a peak stress of 100MPa for 60,000 cycles. Each image is a cross-section taken through the thickness of a Z-binder. A surface view image is attached to each with a red line indicating the position of corresponding cross-section. Blue dashed lines are used to match features on the surface image with the features shown in the cross-section.

4. Concluding remarks

Detailed investigations into damage development during early stage fatigue cycling of a 3D non-crimp orthogonal woven composite have shown some significant differences in the damage morphology for loading in the warp direction compared with loading in the weft direction. For fatigue in the warp-direction damage consisted of weft tow transverse matrix cracks, transverse cracks at the weft tow boundaries or between weft tow boundaries, Z-binder debonds and micro-delaminations between surface weft tows and adjacent warp tows. For fatigue in the weft-direction damage consisted of

transverse warp tow matrix cracks and unusual triangular-shaped damage pairs; these damage pairs consist of interfacial fracture between the Z-binder and the surface weft tow, debonding of the Z-binder from the central weft tow, and interfacial fracture between the central weft tow and the adjacent resin pocket. The relationship between the fatigue damage discussed in this paper and late-stage fatigue damage close to failure of the specimens is the subject of current work.

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